

Iterative (Agile) Modeling Guidelines

Method: Agile / Iterative Tools: ChatGPT / Gemini (As assigned)

Case Study: Parking Lots / Baby Boom (As assigned)

Method Characteristics: Incremental, collaborative, and flexible work process.

Task Overview: You are required to create a UML model for your assigned Case Study (refer to the separate Case Study file) using the assigned tool and following the Iterative workflow defined below.

Required Artifacts:

1. Use Case Diagram (Evolving through iterations)
2. Class Diagram (Evolving through iterations)
3. Sequence Diagram (for the specific scenario defined in Phase 4 below)

General Instructions:

- **Systematic Workflow:** You must work systematically according to the phases detailed below.
- **Tool Interaction:** Use the assigned tool as much as possible. Maintain a dialogue to refine artifacts.
- **Documentation:** Save the chat log in CSV format (using an export plugin) and provide a shared link to the chat.
- **Format:** Diagrams must be in PlantUML format. Ensure the tool provides valid syntax (starting with @startuml and ending with @enduml).
- **Submission:** Submit the final diagrams as .txt files and as image screenshots.

Work Phases

Phase 1: User Story Elicitation

- Read the separate Case Study file carefully.
- Extract User Stories from the text.
- Divide the user stories into four (4) iterations. Each iteration must focus on complete, end-to-end user stories.

Phase 2: Use Case Identification per Iteration

- For each iteration:
 1. Identify the relevant Use Cases.
 2. Create a partial Use Case Diagram for the current iteration.
 3. Document the goal of each Use Case in a single sentence.
 4. Integrate the partial diagram with the Use Case Diagram from previous iterations. Refine and correct as needed.

Phase 3: Just-In-Time Structural Modeling

- For each iteration:
 1. Identify only the concepts and entities required for the current iteration (Nouns = Classes, Verbs = Methods).
 2. Create a partial Class Diagram for the current iteration.
 3. Integrate the partial diagram with the Class Diagram from previous iterations. Refine and correct as needed.

Phase 4: Behavior Modeling (Based on Emergent Behavior)

- If the following scenario is part of the current iteration, create a Sequence Diagram describing its behavior:
 - If assigned Parking Lots: *Generating a Coupon Redemption Report for a Period.*
 - If assigned Baby Boom: *Generating an Abnormal Examination Report for a Baby during a Period.*
- Verify consistency between the Sequence Diagram and the evolving Use Case and Class Diagrams; correct if necessary.